

Efficient Tiny Machine Learning for Human Activity Recognition on Low-Power Edge Devices

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Abstract—Human Activity Recognition (HAR) continues to capture the attention of academic and industrial researchers because of its practical applications in healthcare and everyday living environments. To equate this technology for widespread use, it is crucial to ensure that HAR models are not only high-performing but also optimized for minimal resource usage. This paper employs Tiny Machine Learning (TinyML) techniques, including quantization, pruning, and knowledge distillation for reducing the model size and make a parsimonious use of resources and energy while maintaining high accuracy. The results demonstrate that the proposed approach can reduce the model footprint ($4\times$ on average) with minimized accuracy deviation (4% on average). Additionally, this work extends the deployment of HAR models and the UCI-HAR dataset across three different hardware edge platforms: SensorTile.box PRO embodying multiple sensors, Raspberry Pi, and Arduino. The Arduino exhibited the most efficient use of the energy consumption while the Raspberry Pi the best accuracy.

I. INTRODUCTION

Human Activity Recognition (HAR) is an application domain that addresses the classification problem of basic human activities, for example walking, standing, running, and lying down based on the associated data streams. This area holds a promise of crafting intelligent systems at the edge, where tasks can be deployed instead of the cloud. This includes automating daily chores in smart homes to monitor patients in healthcare settings without expert supervision. Additionally, it plays a vital role in enhancing the quality of life for elderly and less able people through automating their routine tasks based on the observed activity patterns, and supporting these groups with greater safety and care [1].

HAR represents a major time-series analysis challenge, which involves diverse methodologies for capturing and processing data. Among the multiple technologies used, sensor-based distributed and intelligent tiny edge systems have emerged as dominant because of their scalability, accuracy and privacy [2]. HAR typically relies on the use of sensor data to automatically identify and categorize human actions. This technology mitigates risks to personal and property safety by anomaly detection and improves real-time surveillance, reducing the need for any manual analysis. Furthermore, HAR enables behavior analysis and enhances user experience, while also offering guidance, tracking progress, and preventing failures. While video-based systems raise significant complexity and challenges to withholding individual privacy, sensor-based approaches offer a simpler, more trustworthy and effective

means of data collection. In addition to this, the sensor-based approach is proven to be cheaper and more affordable, and with the increasing complexity of wearable sensors, it establishes a clear win over the camera-based systems both in academic as well as industry applications [3].

The field of HAR has evolved remarkably over the past two decades [4]. Initial methods heavily relied upon machine learning (ML) techniques that required hand-crafted feature extraction. These methods account for tasks becoming more time-consuming, less productive and also limit the ability of the ML models to generalize across unseen scenarios. This pushed a major shift towards the advancement of more complex deep learning (DL) approaches that work by leveraging the raw and unprocessed data to learn from and make inferences. The use of DL models allows effective interpretation of complicated, multimodal sensorial data, which results in reduced human intervention and enhances the model’s ability to adapt to new environments [5].

Along with the development of HAR methodologies is the rise of Tiny Machine Learning (TinyML), which addresses the need for highly efficient ML models suitable for deployment on resource-constrained hardware platforms. The role of TinyML becomes more vital on low-power embedded devices, since the high computational demands of large traditional models can not be directly harnessed. TinyML advancements such as power efficiency, enhanced security, as well as low latency response capabilities through multiple optimization techniques and libraries, are essential for HAR applications. This enables HAR systems to operate independently of continuous internet connectivity, so that they become more accessible and sustainable for commercial and wider use. In [6], the authors provided the integration of model compression techniques such as pruning and quantization on Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), Long Short-Term Memory networks (LSTMs), and Multi-Layer LSTMs. The work shows that a HAR model can be significantly reduced in size by as much as $10\times$ without substantially compromising its accuracy or performance.

This paper explores the deployment of a DL-based HAR models on three different available off-the-shelf resource-constrained edge hardware platforms: SensorTile.box PRO, Raspberry Pi, and Arduino, evidencing that Arduino offers the most optimal energy consumption.

The contributions of this paper include the following:

- Analysis of trade-offs between energy consumption and accuracy of HAR models on three hardware platforms.

- Deployment of optimized HAR models on three resource-constrained edge devices such as SensorTile.box PRO, Raspberry Pi, and Arduino.
- A comparative analysis of the performance of HAR models on the above mentioned hardware platforms, which offers a comparative benchmark for future studies and practical deployments in similar contexts.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows: Section II reviews related work of traditional ML and DL in HAR applications. Section III describes how the data was prepared for the development of the CNN, LSTM, and Hybrid models, and the optimizations techniques applied across the three hardware platforms. Section IV defines the experimental setup, the measurement tools, the evaluation metrics and provides evaluation results. Finally, Section V summarizes the main findings and concludes the paper.

II. RELATED WORK

The origin of on-device machine learning (on-device ML) marked a significant shift toward enhancing the resource efficiency, scalability, privacy, sensitivity, and autonomy of edge devices. Initially developed for mobile platforms, on-device ML has gone through substantial refinements, extending its reach to ultra-low-power tiny systems and inside the sensor package. The survey in [7] delves into the significant aspects that are intrinsic to deploying ML models on resource-constrained devices and the different methodologies to analyze and estimate the memory footprint of these models.

One of the very dynamic areas within this expanding field is TinyML, which focuses on the integration of tools, hardware, software, applications, and algorithms designed to perform sensor-specific data analytics deployed on resource-constrained devices [8]. This capability of TinyML is particularly crucial to support a wide range of Internet-of-Things (IoT), automotive, robotics, consumer, and healthcare applications that require always-on functionality in battery-dependent systems.

To enhance efficiency and develop more advanced models, complex techniques such as neural architecture search (NAS) are employed and are specifically optimized for low-power devices [9]. Additionally, various optimization techniques including hyper parameter optimization (HPO), pruning, quantization, and knowledge distillation (KD) are applied to TinyML models to help to maintain high-performance levels.

A. Application of ML in Human Activity Recognition

A variety of algorithms have been utilized in recent years for HAR, mainly relying on supervised learning techniques that require extensive human input for extracting high-level features. Several methods including Principal Component Analysis (PCA), Hidden Markov Models (HMM), Support Vector Machines (SVM), and Random Forest (RF) have been explored to find the most optimal technique. A comparative study involving Multi-Layer Perception (MLP) and Logistic Regression was presented in [10]. While these models have

produced satisfactory outcomes, there are limitations, primarily their dependence on domain-specific knowledge that limits the applications. On the other hand, the work to enhance the accuracy and develop approaches that challenge the constraints of existing domain knowledge of such models continues.

B. Deep Learning in Human Activity Recognition

Recent advancements in DL have significantly improved HAR, where CNNs and RNNs deployment excel on specific hardware yet suffer from limited generalization. A pioneer contribution was outlined in [11], where the authors introduced a three-layer CNN architecture incorporating the variable filter configurations that yielded promising results. Also, in [12] it is detailed a development of two CNN models, called CNN-pf and CNN-pff, both of which achieved accuracy above 90%. In [13] the authors presented an adaptive neuro-fuzzy inference system (ANFIS) integrated with an RNN that achieved a 30.61% improvement in mean squared error (MSE), and 21.21% in mean absolute error (MAE). Further advancements were reported in [14], where a bidirectional LSTM (Bi-LSTM) architecture achieved a top accuracy of 94%.

The exploration of hybrid models combining CNNs and LSTMs has been advantageous, though it remains constrained by the risk of overfitting, limited generalization, and limited optimization. In [15] it was discussed a hybrid CNN-LSTM model that tackled the activity classification challenge and also outperformed both singular LSTM layers and more complex dense LSTM configurations. Another interesting approach was presented in [16], which outperformed all other reviewed models, highlighting the synergistic potential of integrating these two powerful neural network (NN) paradigms in HAR research along with the privacy-centered approach.

III. METHODOLOGY

This section details the methodology employed in this work to optimize a HAR model using a TinyML oriented methodology, which was aimed at reducing memory footprint and computational requirements while maintaining high performance and accuracy. The methodology is structured into four sections as follows: data preparation (Section III-A), model development (Section III-B), model optimization (Section III-C), and model deployment and evaluation on different hardware platforms (Section III-D).

A. Data Preparation

The publicly available UCI-HAR [17] dataset was adopted. It consists of sensor signals from an accelerometer and a gyroscope collected from 30 individuals performing six different activities: walking, walking upstairs, walking downstairs, sitting, standing, and lying down. The data was split into the standard ratio of 70% for training and 30% for testing, and standard pre-processing steps were applied, including normalization to scale the sensor signals and a sliding window approach with a 50% overlap to segment the data into fixed-time intervals, thus providing multiple input batches to the model.

B. Model Development

The development of robust and efficient models is central to advancing HAR technologies, particularly when deploying to three different edge platforms with limited computational resources and power. This research employed a CNN, an RNN, and a Hybrid CNN-RNN model to address the challenge and provide a comprehensive study. Each model was designed to leverage features of sensor data and optimize performance in recognizing human activities efficiently.

1) *Convolutional Neural Network*: The CNN model devised in this study was structured to efficiently process two-dimensional sensor data arrays. The initial model size was 2.4 MB, where the model architecture is comprised of three convolutional layers, each followed by a max pooling layer. The first convolutional layer has 64 filters with a kernel size of 3x3, followed by a second layer of 128 filters and a third layer of 256 filters, both with the 3x3 kernel size. These layers are designed to extract spatial hierarchies of features from the sensor data.

Each convolutional layer utilizes the Rectified Linear Unit (ReLU) activation function to introduce a non-linearity, enhancing the network's ability to learn complex patterns found in the data. Following each convolutional layer, a max pooling layer with a 2x2 window is applied to reduce the spatial dimensions of the feature maps, which resulted in a reduced number of parameters and computations in the network. After the final pooling layer, the feature maps were flattened into a one-dimensional vector to serve as input for the subsequent fully connected layers. The flattened feature vector was then processed through two fully connected layers with 512 and 128 nodes, each followed by a dropout layer with a rate of 0.5 to prevent the possibility of overfitting. The final layer was a softmax layer with six outputs, corresponding to the six activity classes in the initial UCI-HAR dataset.

2) *Recurrent Neural Network*: As the time-series data in HAR was sequential, the RNN model used LSTM units to capture temporal dependencies. The model size was 1.6 MB and consisted of three LSTM layers, each with 100 units. LSTM layers were particularly adept at maintaining information in "memory" for a longer period, which was crucial for time-series analysis. Each LSTM layer was followed by a dropout layer with a rate of 0.2 to reduce overfitting. The sequence of processed data flows through the LSTM layers, enabling the network to learn from long-term dependencies across the time steps. The output from the final LSTM layer passes through a dense layer with a softmax activation function, designed to classify the input sequences into one of the six activities.

3) *Hybrid CNN-RNN*: Post convolution and pooling, the output feature maps were fed into the LSTM layer with 100 units. This complex combination allowed the model to interpret both spatial and temporal dimensions effectively. Following the LSTM layer, the data passed through a fully connected layer with 128 nodes and finally to a softmax output layer for the final activity classification.

C. Model Optimization

1) *Quantization*: Quantization is well known to convert the numerical precision of the DL model parameters from floating points (fp32) to lower-bit representations, typically integers or fractional arithmetic. This conversion significantly reduces the memory footprint, provides opportunities to accelerate computation by using a simpler underlying hardware, and lowers power consumption [18]. Also, by reducing the model's dependence on fp32 arithmetic, quantization facilitated the deployment of models on the three off-the-shelf resource-constrained hardware platforms.

a) *Reduced Precision Float Quantization*: This form of quantization reduces the precision of fp32 numbers used in a model to lower precision of 8-bits(fp8), decreasing the computational load while retaining a degree of floating-point accuracy [19].

b) *Hybrid Quantization*: Hybrid quantization employs a combination of floating-point and integer quantization strategies. This method aims to optimize performance by maintaining critical calculations in floating-point where necessary while using integers for the remainder of the computations [20].

c) *Integer Quantization*: This stringent form of quantization converted all floating-point numbers to integers, which was the most aggressive approach for reducing the computational demands and memory usage [21].

In this paper, following the CNN model training, post-training quantization (PTQ) was applied, converting fp32 weights to 8-bit integers (INT8) without any further fine tuning step. This process helped to significantly reduce the memory footprint of the models. On the other hand, hybrid quantization was applied to the RNN model because of the sequential nature and use of the LSTM unit. This approach combined INT8 quantization for less critical parts of the model with Reduced Precision Float Quantization for key calculations to maintain performance while reducing the computational demand. Finally, for the hybrid CNN-RNN model, integer quantization was applied after the two initial layers to further streamline the computational demands without compromising the model's ability to process data.

2) *Pruning*: Pruning is well-known and used to streamline NN architectures by selectively removing weights that have minimal impact on the model's predictive accuracy. This process involves an iterative method where a fully trained model undergoes repeated cycles of weight elimination over several epochs. The fundamental premise of pruning is to identify and then nullify weights that contribute less to the NN model's outputs. By doing this, it effectively simplifies the model while retaining essential computational paths intact [22].

a) *Structured Pruning*: This approach involves the removal of entire channels or filters within the model, which results in altering both the input and output geometries of the affected layers. Structured pruning can significantly reduce the operational demands of the model and benefit computational efficiency. However, it might compromise the learned model structure, necessitating retraining or architectural adjustments.

b) *Unstructured Pruning*: This method focuses on individual weight elimination by setting specific weights to zero. It preserves the overall architecture of the model as it does not change the dimensional structure of any layer. The primary advantage is that it maintains the integrity of the model’s topology while reducing the number of active neurons.

Structured pruning was adopted iteratively for the CNN model to remove the filters that contributed least to the output until the predetermined level of sparsity was achieved. This was done over multiple cycles, with each of the cycles consisting of a pruning phase followed by a brief retraining period to allow the model to recover from any performance loss. For the RNN and hybrid models, unstructured pruning was applied for individual weights within the LSTM layers to reduce complexity without directly interrupting the sequence processing. Experiments were performed with varying degrees of sparsity, ranging from 50% to 80%, to find the optimal balance between model size reduction and performance retention.

3) *Knowledge Distillation*: Knowledge distillation (KD) is a well known technique, that is widely used for developing HAR systems, where a smaller footprint “student” model is trained to achieve the same functionality of a larger and more complex “teacher” model. The goal is to transfer the knowledge from the teacher model to the student with less weights, thereby enabling the deployment of highly capable models on devices with stringent resource limitations [23].

However, for this study KD was not applied due to 1) the lack of available labeled data required to train the teacher model, and 2) the implementation across three hardware platforms with different processors that could hinder consistent performance and impact model efficiency.

D. Hardware Platforms

To assess the effectiveness of the optimized HAR models, they were deployed on three different off-the-shelf resource-constrained hardware platforms: SensorTile.box PRO, Raspberry Pi, and Arduino. These platforms were selected to represent a diverse range of computing capabilities, power consumption profiles, and typical application scenarios within edge computing. Evaluation metrics including accuracy, memory footprint, and energy consumption were used to provide a comprehensive comparison of models across the platforms.

- 1) SensorTile.box PRO: A compact, sensor-packed module featuring a wide range of built-in sensors that uses an Arm-Cortex-M33 processor with a single-precision FPU and 2 MB of Flash memory. It is ideal for wearable applications because of its small size and extensive sensor integration [24].
- 2) Raspberry Pi: A single-board platform that is known for its balance between performance and power efficiency. It utilizes a quad-core ARM Cortex-A72 processor based on the ARMv8-A architecture with a high-performance FPU supporting both single and double precision operations and memory size of 512 MB, making it suitable for a broader range of edge computing tasks.

Fig. 1. High-level block diagram of the power measurement setup.

- 3) *Arduino*: Known for its ultra-low power consumption and simplicity, it uses an 8-bit AVR microcontroller and 1 MB of Flash memory which is best suited for very simple, low-data-rate applications in highly constrained environments.

Figure 1 provides a high-level overview of the connection of the device under test (DUT) with the Nordic Power Profiler Kit. The Power Profiler app [25] was used to gather the readings from the DUT. The SensorTile.box PRO provides a sensor-packed module, while for Raspberry Pi and Arduino the sensors were connected externally.

IV. EVALUATION

A. Experimental Setup

1) *Deployment Process*: To ensure the seamless operation of the HAR models on the selected hardware platforms, the deployment process was as follows:

a) *Model Conversion*: Initially, the HAR models (developed using TensorFlow) were converted into TensorFlow Lite (TFLite) models. This conversion was critical to adapt the models to the constraints of low-power and resource-constrained platforms. TFLite models were optimized for fast performance on edge computing devices, thus making them ideal for target platforms like Arduino and Raspberry Pi.

b) *Installation*: After conversion, the models were installed on each platform, and run by the TFLite interpreter. This step involved setting up the necessary runtime environment, ensuring that all required TFLite libraries and dependencies were properly configured. The installation process was tailored to each device’s specific software and hardware capabilities to optimize operational efficiency. Especially for SensorTile.box, the Zephyr development environment was used to build and install the application.

c) *Device-Specific Configuration*: After installation, specific configurations were applied for each device. These configurations were essential for fine-tuning the performance of the models, including adjustments to the inference engine parameters that control aspects such as energy consumption and processing speed. Each device was individually calibrated so that it could achieve the best possible balance between computational efficiency and energy use.

2) *Measurement Tools*: To measure the power consumption of each deployed model accurately, the Nordic Power Profiler Kit II [26] was utilized. This off-the-shelf measurement kit provided the ability to track real-time power usage, which was very crucial for evaluating the energy efficiency of the DL models across the three platforms. The Kit allowed the continuous monitoring of energy consumption during model operation. This capability allowed us to gather precise data on how much energy each model consumed under different conditions and configurations.

3) *Evaluation Metrics*: The effectiveness and efficiency of each deployed model were quantitatively assessed using the following metrics:

- 1) *Accuracy*: The model’s ability to accurately classify different human activities. The scores in this metric indicate the effectiveness for real-world applications, ensuring that the HAR system can reliably perform its intended functions.
- 2) *Model Size*: The size of each model was recorded post-optimization. It is a critical factor for model deployment on edge devices, as it affects the feasibility of running advanced algorithms within limited memory capacity.
- 3) *Energy Consumption*: Using data from the power profiler kit, the energy consumption of the model during typical operations was recorded. This helped to determine the practicality of each model for battery-operated scenarios, where energy efficiency is crucial.

B. Results

The three hardware platforms were selected to demonstrate the performance of the models in varying operational environment characteristics of edge computing. The deployment and evaluation of the HAR models highlighted the critical interplay between computational power and energy efficiency in the application of edge computing. To ensure accurate measurements and consistency across all the platforms, version v2.15.0 of TFLite [27] was utilized.

Initially, the energy consumption of each device was recorded by activating the hardware device without any applied computation for a total of 300 seconds to establish a baseline. While measuring the energy consumption per inference, the hardware platforms were configured to perform a single inference repeatedly, along with a cool-down period of 120 seconds between consecutive inferences to minimize any direct thermal effects on the measurement. The power profiler kit recorded the energy consumed from the start to the end of the inference process by triggering the logging function at the start and end of the model’s inference runtime. The energy consumption for a single inference was calculated by integrating the power usage throughout the inference and subtracting the power baseline recorded at the start to make sure that the recorded measurement was based purely on the applied computations involved by the HAR model.

Through the experiment, a standard voltage value for each hardware platform was set up and the fixed execution time of 300 seconds with the sample rate of 1000 per second for

TABLE I
SUMMARY OF ENERGY CONSUMPTION OF THE CNN MODEL.

Hardware Platform	Current (mA)	Voltage (V)	Energy (uJ)
SensorTile.box PRO	11.8	5	59
Raspberry Pi	9.4	5	47
Arduino	5.2	5	26

a better precision was adopted. Table I presents a summary of energy consumption across the hardware platforms running the CNN model, with the energy per inference calculated using Equation 1. The reason for choosing the CNN model as the base for comparison is because the accuracy achieved through it was maximum as compared to the RNN and the hybrid model.

$$\text{Energy per inference (uJ)} = \quad (1)$$

$$= \text{Current} \times \text{Voltage} \times \text{Time per inference} \times 1,000 \quad (2)$$

1) *SensorTile.box PRO*: This platform showed an average current consumption of 11.8 mA. While moderately consuming more current than the Arduino, it offered a balance between energy efficiency and computational power. It is particularly suitable for applications where sensor integration and moderate processing power are required without a significant compromise on energy efficiency.

2) *Raspberry Pi*: This platform demonstrated a current consumption of 9.4 mA, lower than the SensorTile.box PRO despite its higher computational capabilities. This suggests that the Raspberry Pi offers an improved energy management and efficiency, making it a better option for more demanding tasks with substantial consideration of energy usage.

3) *Arduino*: This platform is known for its simplicity and extremely low power consumption, and provided the lowest current consumption at 5.2 mA. Arduino is ideal for deploying simplistic, long-term monitoring applications where energy availability is very limited.

The accuracy of the CNN, RNN and Hybrid models deployed across the three hardware platforms is presented in Table II, showing the performance of each platform for classifying activities. For evaluating accuracy across the three hardware platforms, the employed testing methodology involved randomizing the selection of test sets three times to assess the robustness and generalization of the performance. Interestingly, because of the use of randomized test sets, an average deviation of 4% in the accuracy of the models was observed.

The mean accuracy was calculated to get a comparative overview of the models over the hardware platforms, shown in Table II. SensorTile.box PRO achieved a mean accuracy of 90.6% with a variance of 0.67 for CNN, 1.72 for LSTM, and 2.28 for the Hybrid model respectively. The Raspberry Pi achieved the highest accuracy of 92.7%, with a variance of 4.21 for CNN, 2.5 for LSTM, and 0.84 for the Hybrid model respectively, which suggests its potential for a more processing intensive tasks. The Arduino while offering the advantage of extremely low energy consumption, shows a

TABLE II

MODEL ACCURACY (%) COMPARISON ACROSS HARDWARE. DIFFERENT RESULTS PER MODEL ARE DUE TO DIFFERENT RANDOMIZATIONS TO EXTRACT THE TEST SETS.

Hardware Platform	CNN INT8	LSTM FP32	Hybrid FP32-FP8
SensorTile.box PRO	92.5	91.0	88.4
Raspberry Pi	94.8	93.2	90.2
Arduino	89.4	86.4	82.3

TABLE III

CNN MODEL SIZE AND PARAMETER COMPARISON. NON-TRAINABLE PARAMETERS ARE ALWAYS ZERO.

Hardware Platform	Model Size	Trainable Parameters
SensorTile.box PRO	320 KiB	16,560
Raspberry Pi	600 KiB	23,750
Arduino	150 KiB	2,360

lower mean accuracy of 86.0% with variance 2.52 for CNN, 0.48 for LSTM, and 1.39 for the Hybrid model respectively.

Finally, the size of the deployed models was a critical factor, particularly for resource-constrained edge devices where memory capacity and processing power are very limited. Table III shows a comparative overview of the CNN model size across the three hardware platforms, reflecting the impact of the applied optimization techniques. Note that the difference in the model sizes across the three platforms is due to the use of different programming languages, frameworks, tools, and libraries during development and deployment process.

The model size for the SensorTile.box PRO was reduced to 320 KiB, which is well-suited to its 2MB memory size, and achieves an accuracy of 92.5%. The Raspberry Pi, accommodating the largest model size at 600 KiB and leveraging 512MB of available memory, achieved an accuracy of 94.8%, indicative of its application in scenarios requiring high processing power with less concern for memory limitations. Conversely, the Arduino supports the smallest model size at 150 KiB with a lower accuracy of 89.4%, which is decent considering the availability of 1MB in memory. The smaller size is essential for its deployment in severely resource-constrained settings, where minimal storage and processing capabilities are vital.

V. CONCLUSION

This work demonstrated the application of TinyML techniques (such as pruning and quantization) to optimize HAR models, addressing the challenge of minimizing model size and thus the use of computational resources while maintaining high accuracy. Notably, the deployment of HAR models on different resource-constrained edge computing platforms (such as SensorTile.box PRO, Raspberry Pi, and Arduino) has provided crucial insights into the practical implications of computational and energy efficiency in real-world scenarios. Future developments will include other approaches such as the RNN's legendre memory unit (LMU) based topologies.

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